

**ANTIBACTERIAL ANALYSIS OF *Muntingia calabura* (MANSANITAS)
ETHANOLIC FLOWER EXTRACT ON *Staphylococcus aureus* USING
PAPER DISC DIFFUSION METHOD**

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ABSTRACT

The rise of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains, particularly *Staphylococcus aureus*, necessitates the exploration of novel antimicrobial agents derived from natural sources. This study evaluated the antibacterial efficacy of *Muntingia calabura* ethanolic flower extract against *S. aureus* using the paper disc diffusion method. The extract was obtained through maceration in 96% ethanol, followed by filtration and concentration under reduced pressure. Three independent trials were conducted to measure the diameter of the zone of inhibition (ZOI) induced by the extract. The results demonstrated a significant antibacterial effect, with an average ZOI of 29 mm, with a standard deviation of ± 1.53 mm, indicating consistent results across three trials. This result classifies the extract as "very active" based on standard interpretative criteria. The absence of inhibition in the control confirmed the bioactivity of the extract rather than external variables. These findings suggest that *M. calabura* possesses potent antimicrobial properties, potentially attributed to its bioactive phytochemicals such as flavonoids, tannins, and polyphenols. However, further research is required to isolate and characterize the active compounds, elucidate their mechanisms of action, and assess their clinical applicability. Additionally, toxicity and cytotoxicity studies must be undertaken to ensure the extract's safety for pharmaceutical use. The results of this study contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting plant-based antibacterial agents as viable alternatives to conventional antibiotics, particularly in the face of escalating antimicrobial resistance.

Keywords: antibacterial; *Muntingia calabura*; *Staphylococcus aureus*; zone of inhibition

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study would not have been possible without the unwavering support from the people around me, who helped me stay strong and overcome adversities in this journey. I would like to extend my deepest gratitude to the following people who not only became my rock, but also became a guiding light.

To my father and mother, **Frederick Collantes** and **Reichelle Yap**, for their words of encouragement and for helping me find my mansanitas flower samples.

To my sisters, **Frenchella and Freyanna Collantes**, for believing in me.

To my **friends**, whom each of us shared our insights in this path of research.

And to my research adviser, **Ma'am Merriam Danielle G. Tarre** for her guidance and patience throughout my research journey.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Throughout history, *Muntingia calabura*, often referred to as Jamaican cherry, has served a variety of functions in many civilizations. These functions include medicinal (Muhammad et al., 2021), nutritional (Mastuki, 2019), cultural, and ecological uses. According to Rakesh, et al. (2023), the fruits of *Muntingia calabura* have substantial anti-inflammatory properties. The blossoms have antibacterial and antispasmodic properties, when used to make therapeutic drinks. In the review of the Mahmood (2014), the traditional uses of *Muntingia calabura* flowers has been stated, including: flowers and bark are used in Peruvian folklore medicine as an antiseptic and to reduce swelling in the lower limbs, while leaves (boiled or steeped) are employed to treat gastric ulcers and prostate gland swelling, as well as to relieve headaches and colds; In Colombia, the flower infusion serves as a tranquilizer and tonic; In the Philippines, the flowers are utilized for treating headaches and early signs of colds, as well as serving as tranquilizers, antispasmodics, and antidyspeptics. Lastly, the leaves of *Muntingia calabura* (M. Calabura) showed potential antioxidant and anti-proliferative properties. The properties of the fruits, leaves, and bark of *Muntingia calabura* is extensively studied, however, there is limited research on the properties of its flowers. A study conducted by St. Mary et al. (2024), indicate that the Jamaican cherry flower ethanol extracts have strong antibacterial qualities against common gastrointestinal infections as *Vibrio cholerae*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, and *Escherichia coli*.

Staphylococcus aureus is a species of bacteria that can be found on the skin and in the nose of approximately 30% of humans (U.S. Centers for Disease and Control Prevention, 2024). Although it frequently coexists innocuously as a component of the normal microbiota, it has the potential to turn pathogenic and cause a number of illnesses (Taylor and Unakal, 2023). These infections can range in severity from simple skin problems like cellulitis and boils to more serious illnesses like sepsis, pneumonia, and endocarditis. Furthermore, it was found in a study conducted by Pantosti et al. (2007) that more than any other human pathogen, *Staphylococcus aureus* can be used to illustrate the adaptive evolution of bacteria during the antibiotic era due to the fact that it has shown a remarkable capacity to rapidly develop a resistance mechanism to each new antibiotic, from penicillin and methicillin to the most recent ones, linezolid and daptomycin. This finding further prompts the researchers for a better antibiotic to counteract the resistance mechanism of a *Staphylococcus aureus*.

This study aims to determine the antibacterial potential of *Muntingia calabura* ethanolic flower extract on *Staphylococcus aureus* using the paper disc diffusion method.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to determine the antibacterial potential of *Muntingia calabura* ethanolic flower extract on *Staphylococcus aureus*. Specifically, the study aims to:

1.2.1 Produce an ethanolic extract from the maceration of *Muntingia calabura* flowers in 96% ethanol solvent.

1.2.2 Measure and record the diameter of Zone of Inhibition (ZOI) of *S. aureus* after treatment with *M. calabura* ethanolic flower extract using paper disc diffusion method.

Commented [1]: 1.2.1 Identify the sample species of Mansanitas

1.3 Significance of the Study

Pharmacological Advancement. The foundation of new drugs and the progress of pharmacology are antibiotic and antibacterial research. This research contributes to the body of knowledge of herbal pharmacology.

Medicinal Advancement. The results of this study will contribute to the field of medicine, providing a potential alleviation of certain symptoms of diseases.

Microbiological and Bacterial Understanding. Observation of the reaction of the *S. aureus* to the treatment will provide us with further understanding of microbiology and bacteria.

This research can also contribute to accomplishing the following **United Nation**

Sustainable Development Goals:

Good Health and Well-being (SDG 3) End the epidemics of communicable diseases. *Streptococcus pyogenes* is a bacterial pathogen responsible for diseases like strep throat and skin infections. Effective

treatments, especially those derived from natural sources, contribute to controlling and reducing the incidence of such infections.

Achieve universal health coverage. Affordable and accessible treatments are essential for achieving universal health coverage. Natural remedies like *Muntingia calabura* fruit extract could provide alternative or complementary options, especially in resource-limited settings.

Responsible Consumption and Production (SDG 12) Support the development of sustainable practices. Utilizing plant-based extracts from local or underutilized resources like *Muntingia calabura* for medical purposes can promote the sustainable use of biodiversity and encourage the responsible consumption of natural resources.

Life on Land (SDG 15) Protect and prevent the extinction of threatened species. The promotion and sustainable use of native plant species like *Muntingia calabura* can contribute to biodiversity conservation and the protection of ecosystems where these plants are found.

1.4 Scope and Limitations

This study only focuses on the antibacterial effects of the ethanol extract from the flowers of *M. calabura* on *S. aureus*. Furthermore, the testing process will be conducted only on the Microbiological Laboratory of the Department of Science and Technology- CARAGA.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 *Muntingia calabura*

Note. Figure 1. The various parts of *M. calabura*. (a) The tree of *M. calabura*. (b) The leaves of *M. calabura*. (c) The flower of *M. calabura*. (d) The unripe fruit of *M. calabura*. (e) The ripe fruit of *M. calabura*. (f) The dissected ripe fruit of *M. calabura*. Images retrieved from Mahmood et. al., (2014)

Muntingia calabura, also known as the Jamaica cherry, is a small evergreen tree that ranges in height from 3 to 12 meters and is a minor fruit species that blooms

continually. It is native to southern Mexico, Central America, northern South America, and the Greater Antilles. However, it has spread to many other countries, including Southeast Asia, where people mistakenly believe it to be local because of its excellent adaptation and abundance of trees (Berazain, 2016).

This tree grows quickly and has slender dimensions, rising to a height of roughly 7.5–12 meters with branches that expand horizontally (Figure 1a). The foliage of *M. calabura* has a length of 5 to 12.5 cm, alternately long and pointed at the tip, lanceolate or oblong, slant at the base, dark green in color, and minutely hairy on the upper surface; underside is unevenly toothed and has gray or brown hair. The flowers, which have five green sepals, five white petals, and numerous noticeable yellow stamens, are about 1.25 to 2 centimeters wide and are borne singly, in pairs, or in threes in the leaf axils (Figure 1c). The fruits are abundant, spherical, and between 1-1.25 centimeters across. They have thin, smooth, fragile skin that is red or yellow, and a light-brown, soft, juicy pulp that tastes very sweet and musky, like figs. The pulp is also packed with incredibly small, yellowish seeds (Figure 1d) (Morton, 1987).

Pharmacological Properties of *Muntingia calabura*

According to the review of Mahmood et. al. (2014), the pharmacological properties of *M. calabura* includes having cytotoxic activity (Kaneda et. al., 1991), antiproliferative activity (Zakaria et. al., 2011), quinone reductase activity (Su et. al., 2003), antiplatelet aggregation activity (Chen et al., 2007), antioxidant activity (Zakaria et. al., 2007), insecticidal activity (Bandeira et. al., 2013), antinociceptive activity (Zakaria et al., 2006), anti-inflammatory activity (Zakaria et. al., 2007),

antipyretic activity (Zakaria et al., 2007), antiulcer activity (Ibrahim et al., 2012), antidiabetic activity (Sridhar et al., 2011), antihypertensive activity (Shih et al., 2006), and cardioprotective activity (Nivethetha et. al., 2009)

The earliest attempt to study the antibacterial properties of *M. calabura* was conducted by Yasunaka et al. (2005) using the methanol extract from its fruits and leaves, diluted in 100 mg/mL of DMSO concentration and then subjected to two-fold serial dilutions, and then tested against *Escherichia coli* (C600) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (209 P) using the micro-dilution assay. The results showed that the extract shows antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, with a recorded MIC of 512 and 1024 mg/mL, and 128 and 256 mg/mL, respectively.

2.2 Antibacterial Activity of *Muntingia calabura* Ethanolic Flower Extract

A study conducted by St. Mary et al. (2024) showed that the ethanolic extract of *Muntingia calabura* flowers had a significant antibacterial effect against pathogens that caused gastrointestinal infections. The study tested the extract against *Salmonella typhi* (NCTC 786), *Vibrio cholerae* (ATCC 27853), and *Shigella dysenteriae* (ATCC 25923).

2.3 *Staphylococcus aureus*

Note. Figure 2. SEM of *Staphylococcus aureus*. retrieved from <https://phil.cdc.gov/details.aspx?pid=11155>.

The 1880s saw the discovery of *Staphylococcus aureus*. Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* is a bacterium that creates asymmetrical bunches that resemble grapes (Greek: staphyle, bunch of grapes; kokkus, berry). It is catalase positive, non-motile, and non-spore-forming. In aerobic circumstances, it develops quickly and in large quantities. According to Foster (2002), the natural habitat of *Staphylococcus aureus* in humans is the epidermis and nasopharynx. It can induce a wide variety of infections including skin and soft tissues, endovascular locations and internal organs. *Staphylococcus aureus* continues to be a major pathogen in the community and in hospitals, generating substantial morbidity and mortality. The organism can be spread from a surface site via the bloodstream to internal organs where it can establish a metastatic focus of infection. Major sites of infection in hospital patients are surgical wounds and indwelling medical equipment. The characteristics to be mentioned are according to the review of Foster (2002)

2.3.1 Classification

The genus *Staphylococcus* belongs to the large *Bacillus-Lactobacillus-Streptococcus* cluster, according to molecular taxonomic research (Ludwig et al., 1985; Teuber and Stackebrandt, 1988), and it is the most closely associated with *Listeria*, *Bacillus*, and *Enterococcus*.

2.3.2 Identification

Colonies of *Staphylococcus aureus* are elevated, smooth, shiny, translucent, and frequently have a golden hue. It is possible to grow halotolerant *Staphylococci* on mannitol salt agar, which contains 7.5% sodium chloride, by plating specimens that are likely to be contaminated with other microbes. If not, erythrocytes may be included in the streaking of bacteria on trypticase soy agar. *Staphylococcus aureus* small colony variations must be carefully identified because they can occasionally be overlooked.

2.3.3 Immunity

Both humans and animals in good health have a high level of inherent defense against *Staphylococcus aureus*-induced invasive infections. It is challenging to prove an infection in humans, animals, or laboratories (Elek and Conch, 1987). A significant number of germs or the presence of a foreign body are necessary for infection. Surface barriers, cellular immunity, and humoral immunity are the causes of this innate immunity (reviewed by Verhoef; 1997). The primary element of the host defense is PMNLs. As a result, people who have deficiencies in PMNL

function frequently have staphylococcal infections. *Staphylococcus aureus* cells are quickly destroyed after being phagocytosed.

Since then, it has been demonstrated to be a potentially harmful Gram-positive bacterium that can cause infections such as mild skin infections and wound infections following surgery. Before penicillin was developed to treat *Staphylococcus aureus* infections in the early 1940s, the mortality rate for those infected with the bacteria was over 80%. (Deurenberg and Stobberingh, 2008). Two years after penicillin was first used in medicine, in 1942, a hospital reported the first isolate of *Staphylococcus aureus* that was resistant to the antibiotic. Later, strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* that were resistant to penicillin were also found in the population. Approximately 80% of all strains of *Staphylococcus aureus* have been penicillin-resistant since 1960.

2.3.4 Antimicrobials used for *Staphylococcus aureus* treatment

There have been reviews of treatment options for invasive *Staphylococcus aureus* infections (Graninger et al., 1995; Waldvogel, 1995; Chambers, 1997; Hooper, 1997). Until it is demonstrated that the organism does not generate 3 lactamase, a penicillinase-resistant penicillin should be used for treatment. At that point, penicillin G can be utilized. The recommended treatment for methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) infections is still intravenous vancomycin. Aminoglycosides and fluoroquinolones were recently introduced to fight MRSA, but their effectiveness has been jeopardized by the quick emergence of resistance.

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

The methodology used in this study will test the antibacterial potential of *Muntingia calabura* (Mansanitas) ethanolic flower extract against *Staphylococcus aureus*. This testing will be held at the Department of Science and Technology-CARAGA, by implementing three (3) trials (Trial 1, Trial 2, Trial 3) using the Assay method of paper disc diffusion (6mm diameter disc) in a nutrient agar solution seeded with *Staphylococcus aureus* (BIOTECH 1582). The procedure for the conduct of antimicrobial screening was obtained from the book entitled “A Guidebook to Plant Screening: Phytochemical and Biological” (Claustra et. al, 2005).

Figure 3. Flowchart

3.1 Collection of Plant Material

The *Muntingia calabura* flowers were collected in January 2025 from the local vicinity in Cabadbaran City, Agusan del Norte. The flowers were cleaned using water and weighed to be approximately 49.14 g.

Commented [2]: Identify Botanist

3.2 Plant Extract Preparation

Maceration was done to extract the potential antibacterial bioactive compounds present in *Muntingia calabura*. The sample was soaked in 300mL of 96% ethanol solvent (St. Mary et al., 2024) for 34 days.

Figure 3. Maceration of *Muntingia calabura* flowers in 300mL of 96% ethanol extract

After maceration, the sample was strained and filtered to remove the marc (the damp solid material), and pressed. To isolate the extract, the ethanol solvent

was evaporated using a rotary evaporator with a temperature of 40°C (Buhian, 2016) and set to a reduced pressure.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Filtration of sample (a) using a plastic strainer. (b) using filter paper.

Figure 5. Separation of Ethanol solvent from *Muntingia calabura* flower extract using a rotary evaporator.

Figure 6. Pure *M. calabura* extracted flower extract (15mL)

3.3 Preparation of *Staphylococcus aureus* Inoculum

3.3.1 Preparation of 0.5 M McFarland Standard

The 0.5 M McFarland standard will be used to adjust the turbidity of *Staphylococcus aureus* before the application via swabbing of the agar plates for the antimicrobial assays. This standard is necessary to ensure quality control before usage. It was prepared by mixing 0.5 mL of 0.048 BaCl₂ (1.175% w/v BaCl₂*2H₂O) to 99.5 mL of H₂SO₄ (1% v/v); The standard was then distributed by 5mL in screw-cap tubes similar in dimension, as those to be used in preparation of the *Staphylococcus aureus* suspension. Prior to its usage, it was placed in a mechanical vortex mixture to shake the turbidity.

3.3.2 Preparation of Nutrient Broth

A loopful of *Staphylococcus aureus* was extracted from the culture slant and inoculated into 50 mL of nutrient broth. The culture broth was incubated for 18 to 24 hours at a temperature of 35°C.

3.3.3 Adjustment of the Turbidity of *Staphylococcus aureus* Inoculum

A vortex mixer was used to stir the suspension of *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria, which was then compared to the 0.5 McFarland standard.

3.4 Preparation of Trials

There will be three (3) trials to be conducted inside a petri dish. Approximately 15mL of melted nutrient agar was poured into a dry and sterile petri dish and solidified.

3.5 Cotton Swabbing of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Using a sterile cotton swab, *Staphylococcus aureus* was transferred onto the solidified nutrient agar by dipping the cotton swab into a suspension of *S. aureus*, then it is pressed and rotated firmly against the inside of the wall to remove the excess liquid. The swab is then streaked across the entire surface of the agar plate three (3) times, with a 60-degree rotation of the plate after each application to achieve an even distribution of bacteria on the medium's surface. Leave the swabbed plates for 5 minutes.

3.6 Application of *Muntingia calabura* Flower Extract

The assay method used to administer *Muntingia calabura* flower extract onto the trials was paper disc diffusion method. Three (3) pieces of 6mm paper discs were immersed into the *Muntingia calabura* flower extract laid in a nutrient agar solution streaked with *Staphylococcus aureus*

Figure 7. Three (3) trials made of 6mm paper discs immersed in *Muntingia calabura* flower extract laid in a nutrient agar solution streaked with *Staphylococcus aureus*

3.7 Measurement of the Zone of Inhibition (ZOI)

The circular area around the antibiotic spot, which can be described as a “halo” or “clearing” surrounding the discs (Claustra et. al, 2005), where bacteria colonies do not grow is known as the Zone of inhibition (ZOI) (Bhargav, 2016).

The ZOI will be used as an indicator of how susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus* will be when in contact with *Muntingia calabura* flower extract.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of the treatment of *Staphylococcus aureus* with *Muntingia calabura* ethanolic flower extract. The Zone of Inhibition (ZOI) of the ethanolic flower extract of *Muntingia calabura* flowers against *Staphylococcus aureus* was measured.

Parameter	Zone of Inhibition (mm)
Control	0
Trial 1	29
Trial 2	31
Trial 3	28
Average	29

Note: Analysis of Result: <10mm, inactive. 10-13mm, partially active. 14-19mm, active. >19 mm, very active

Table 1 Measurement of Zone of Inhibition (ZOI) against *Staphylococcus aureus* of the three (3) trials of paper discs treated with *Muntingia calabura* flower extract

The ethanolic flower extract of *Muntingia calabura* demonstrated significant antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, with Trial 1 exhibiting a ZOI of 29mm, Trial 2 with 31mm, and Trial 3 with 28mm. The mean Zone of Inhibition (ZOI) is 29 mm across the trials. According to the interpretation criteria, inhibition zones exceeding 19 mm are classified as "very active," indicating that the extract possesses potent antimicrobial properties. The absence of inhibition in the control confirms the bioactivity of the extract rather than external factors.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary

This study investigated the antibacterial activity of *Muntingia calabura* (mansanitas) ethanolic flower extract against *Staphylococcus aureus* using the paper disc diffusion method. The plant extract was obtained through maceration in 96% ethanol, followed by filtration and concentration under reduced pressure. The antibacterial assay was conducted by using three (3) trials, impregnating three sterile paper discs with the extract and measuring the zone of inhibition against *S. aureus*. The results showed that *Muntingia calabura* flower extract exhibited a measurable zone of inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus*, indicating the presence of bioactive compounds with potential antimicrobial properties.

5.2 Conclusion

The findings of this study provided empirical evidence supporting the antibacterial potential of *Muntingia calabura* ethanolic flower extract against *Staphylococcus aureus*. The presence of inhibitory activity suggested that the extract contained bioactive phytochemicals with antimicrobial properties, reinforcing its traditional medicinal applications.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the following are recommended for the improvement of findings:

1. Include varying concentrations and increase the number of trials.
2. Focus on isolating and identifying the specific bioactive compounds responsible for the antibacterial activity of *Muntingia calabura* flower extract.
3. Investigate the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of the extract to determine the exact concentration required for effective bacterial inhibition.

Bibliography

- Bhargav, H. S., et al. "Measurement of the Zone of Inhibition of an Antibiotic." *Measurement of the Zone of Inhibition of an Antibiotic*, Feb. 2016, pp. 409–14. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iacc.2016.82>.
- Buhian, William Patrick Cruiz, et al. "Bioactive Metabolite Profiles and Antimicrobial Activity of Ethanolic Extracts From *Muntingia Calabura* L. Leaves and Stems." *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, vol. 6, no. 8, June 2016, pp. 682–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apjtb.2016.06.006>.
- CDC. (2024, April 15). *Staphylococcus Aureus Basics*. CDC. <https://www.cdc.gov/staphylococcus-aureus/about/index.html>
- Claustra, A. L., Madulid, R. S., Aguinaldo, A. M., Espeso, E. I., Guevara, B. Q., Nonato, M. G., ... & Ysrael, M. C. (2005). A guidebook to plant screening:

- Phytochemical and biological. University of Santo Tomas Publishing House, Espana, Manila, 105-120.
- Deurenberg, R. H., & Stobberingh, E. E. (2008). The evolution of *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*, 8(6), 747–763. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2008.07.007>
- Ibrahim, J., Eisen, J. A., Jospin, G., Coil, D. A., Khazen, G., & Tokajian, S. (2016). Genome Analysis of *Streptococcus pyogenes* Associated with Pharyngitis and Skin Infections. *PLOS ONE*, 11(12), e0168177. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0168177>
- J. Foster, T. (2002, January 1). 39 - *Staphylococcus aureus* (M. Sussman, Ed.). ScienceDirect; Academic Press. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/B9780126775303502580>
- Mahmood, N. D., Nasir, N. L. M., Rofiee, M. S., Tohid, S. F. M., Ching, S. M., Teh, L. K., Salleh, M. Z., & Zakaria, Z. A. (2014). Muntingia calabura: A review of its traditional uses, chemical properties, and pharmacological observations. *Pharmaceutical Biology*, 52(12), 1598–1623. <https://doi.org/10.3109/13880209.2014.908397>
- Maryam, St., Fitriana, F., & Annisa, N. (2024). Antibacterial Activity in Ethanol Extract of Kersen Flowers (*Muntingia calabura* L.) Against Bacteria Causing Gastrointestinal Tract Infections Using the Agar Diffusion Method. *Journal Microbiology Science*, 4(2), 259–270. <https://doi.org/10.56711/jms.v4i2.1157>
- Mastuki, S. N., Faudzi, S. M. M., Ismail, N., & Saad, N. (2019). Muntingia calabura: Chemical Composition, Bioactive Component and Traditional Uses. *Wild Fruits: Composition, Nutritional Value and Products*, 549–564. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-31885-7_41
- Muhammad Ansori, A. N., Kharisma, V. D., & Intan Solikhah, T. (2021). Medicinal properties of *Muntingia calabura* L.: A Review. *Research*

Journal of Pharmacy and Technology, 14(8), 4509–4512.
<https://doi.org/10.52711/0974-360x.2021.00784>

N. Chaudhari, R., Kumar Jain, A., & K. Chatap, V. (2022). An Overview on Phytochemistry, Pharmacology, and Traditional aspects of *Muntingia calabura*. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*, 2814–2820.
<https://doi.org/10.52711/0974-360x.2022.00470>

Pantosti, A., Sanchini, A., & Monaco, M. (2007). Mechanisms of antibiotic resistance in *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Future Microbiology*, 2(3), 323–334.
<https://doi.org/10.2217/17460913.2.3.323>

St. Mary, et al. “Antibacterial Activity in Ethanol Extract of Kersen Flowers (*Muntingia calabura*L.) Against Bacteria Causing Gastrointestinal Tract Infections Using the Agar Diffusion Method.” *Journal Microbiology Science*, vol. Vol.4, no. 2, Apr. 2024,
<https://doi.org/10.56711/jms.v4i2.1157>.

Taylor, T. A., & Unakal, C. G. (2023, July 17). *Staphylococcus aureus Infection*. Nih.gov; StatPearls Publishing.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK441868/>

APPENDICES

Appendix A

TABLE 2. Task list of the Research Project.

TASK CODE	TASK DESCRIPTION	IMMEDIATELY PRECEDING TASK	ESTIMATED DURATION (in days)
A	Procurement of <i>Muntingia calabura</i> flowers	-	5
B	Maceration of the collected flowers	-	34

C	Filtration	A,B	1
D	Evaporation of Ethanol Solvent using Rotary Evaporator	C	2
E	Preparation 0.05 M McFarland Standard for <i>S. aureus</i> Inoculum	-	1
F	Preparation Nutrient Broth for <i>S. aureus</i> Inoculum	-	1
G	Adjustment of Turbidity and Comparison of <i>S. aureus</i> Inoculum	F	1
H	Preparation of Nutrient Agar	-	1
I	Cotton Swabbing of <i>S. aureus</i> on Nutrient Agar	H	1
J	Application of <i>M. calabura</i> Flower Extract using Paper Disc Diffusion Method	H	1
K	Observance of the presence of a Zone of Inhibition (ZOI)	I,J	1
L	Data Collection	K	2

Appendix B

Figure 8. Network chart of the Research Project.

Appendix C

Figure 9. Gantt chart with indicated slack times

Appendix D

Table 3. Manpower assignment of tasks to members

TASK CODE	TASK DESCRIPTION	RESEARCH IN CHARACTER	IMMEDIATELY PRECEDING	ESTIMATED DURATION (in	EARLIEST START TIME (EST)	TARGET START DATE	LATEST START TIME	LATEST COMPLETION TIME
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		RGE	TASK	days)				(LCT)
A	Procurement of <i>Muntingia calabura</i> flowers	ALL	-	5	Jan 7	Jan 7	Jan 10	Jan 13
B	Maceration of the collected flowers	ALL	-	2	Jan 13	Jan 13	Jan 14	Feb 17
C	Filtration	ALL	A,B	1	Feb 17	Feb 17	Feb 17	Feb 17
D	Evaporation of Ethanol Solvent using Rotary Evaporator	ALL	C	2	Feb 17	Feb 17	Feb 25	Feb 26
E	Preparation 0.05 M McFarland Standard for <i>S. aureus</i> Inoculum	ALL	D	3	Feb 26	Feb 26	March 12	March 14
F	Preparation Nutrient Broth for <i>S. aureus</i> Inoculum	ALL	-	3	Feb 26	Feb 26	March 12	March 14
G	Adjustment of Turbidity	ALL	F	3	Feb 26	Feb 26	March 12	March 14

	and Comparis on of <i>S.</i> <i>aureus</i> Inoculum							
H	Preparatio n of Nutrient Agar	ALL	G	3	Feb 26	Feb 26	March 12	March 14
I	Cotton Swabbing of <i>S.</i> <i>aureus</i> on Nutrient Aga	ALL	H	3	Feb 26	Feb 26	March 12	March 14
J	Applicati on of <i>M.</i> <i>calabura</i> Flower Extract using Paper Disc Diffusion Methodr	ALL	H	3	Feb 26	Feb 26	March 12	March 14
K	Observan ce of the presence of a Zone of Inhibition (ZOI)	ALL	I,J	3	Feb 26	Feb 26	March 12	March 14
L	Data	ALL	K	3	March 14	March 14	March 20	March

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Appendix E

Table 4. Material sourcing plan

PROTOCOL	DATE NEEDED	QTY / UNIT	MATERIALS NEEDED	POTENTIAL SOURCE(S)	REMARKS
Procurement of <i>Muntingia calabura</i> flowers	Feb 10	100g	Basket	Local Vicinity of Cabadbaran & Butuan City	Researcher will hand-pick the flowers

Maceration of <i>Muntingia calabura</i> flowers using 96% Ethanol Solvent	Feb 17	350 g	<i>Muntingia calabura</i> flowers	PSHS-CRC Science Laboratory	Researcher will conduct this with the aid of the Science Laboratory Supervisor
Evaporation of Ethanol Solvent using Rotary Evaporator	Feb 26	50g	Rotary Evaporator	PSHS-CRC Science Laboratory	Researcher will conduct this with the aid of the Science Laboratory Supervisor
Microbial Analysis of <i>Muntingia calabura</i> flower extract against <i>Staphylococcus</i>	March 1	50g	Mueller-Hinton agar plates, sterile cotton swabs, antimicrobial disks, 0.5 McFarland turbidity	DOST- CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory	DOST-CARAGA Laboratory specialists will conduct the experimentation.

<i>aureus</i>			standard, forceps, ruler, nutrient broth		
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Appendix F

Table 5. Equipment sourcing plan

PROTOCOL	DATE NEEDED	QTY / UNIT	EQUIPMENTS NEEDED	POTENTIAL SOURCE(S)	REMARKS
Maceration of <i>Muntingia calabura</i> flowers	Feb 26	1 unit	Beaker, 96% Ethanol Solvent	PSHS- CRC Science Lab	Laboratory Request and Equipment Accountability Form; Reserve before use

Evaporation of Ethanol Solvent	Feb 27	1 unit	Rotary Evaporator	PSHS-CRC Science Lab	Laboratory Request and Equipment Accountability Form; Reserve before use
Paper disc diffusion method of <i>M. calabura</i> flower extract against <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	March 14	1 unit	Mueller-Hinton agar plates, <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> culture, antimicrobial disks, sterile swabs, a McFarland standard, ruler, forceps, incubator	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory	Facilitating of this procedure will be done by DOST-CARAGA Laboratory Specialists

Appendix G

Table 6. Facilities sourcing plan

PROTOCOL	DATE NEEDED	FACILITIES NEEDED	POSSIBLE LOCATIONS	REMARKS
Maceration and Ethanol Evaporation Area	Feb 15 - March 10	Chemistry Laboratory	PSHS-CRC Chemistry Laboratory	Submit Laboratory Request and Equipment Accountability Form

Paper disc diffusion method	March 12	Microbiology Laboratory	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory	Submit Microbial Analysis Request and Flower Extract to DOST-CARAGA
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Appendix H

Table 7. Projected Expenses for the Research Project

		QUANTITY / UNIT		UNIT COST	REQUIRED BUDGET	PROCUREMENT SOURCE / REMARKS
Personnel Services						
	none			-	-	n/a
Consumable Materials						
	none			-	-	n/a
Non-consumable Materials						
	<i>Muntingia calabura</i> flowers	50	g	-	-	Local vicinity of Butuan and Cabadbaran City
	Basket	1	pc			Owned by Researcher
	96% Ethanol Solvent	300	g	-	-	PSHS-CRC Science Laboratory
	Beaker	1	pc	-	-	PSHS-CRC Science Laboratory
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (BIOTECH 1582) culture	-	-	-	-	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory
	Petri dish	1	pc	-	-	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory
	Mueller-Hinton agar	-	-	-	-	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards

						Testing Laboratory
	Sterile Cotton Swabs	5	pcs	-	-	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory
	0.5 McFarland turbidity standard	5	mL	-	-	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory
	forceps	1	pc	-	-	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory
	Ruler	1	pc	-	-	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory
	Nutrient broth	-	-	-	-	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory
	Glass container	1	pc			Owned by researcher
	Equipment					
	Rotary Evaporator	1	unit	-	-	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laboratory
	Facilities					
	Maceration and Rotary Evaporation area			-	-	PSHS-CRC Science Laboratory
	Microbiological Laboratory			-	-	DOST-CARAGA Regional Standards Testing Laborator
	Total Budget: -					

Appendix I

Table 8. Task List and corresponding observable indicators

TASK CODE	TASK DESCRIPTION	IMMEDIATELY PRECEDING TASKS	ESTIMATED DURATION (in days)	OBSERVABLE INDICATORS
A	Procurement of <i>Muntingia calabura</i> flowers	-	3	Will be procured from the gardening market
B	Maceration of the collected flowers	-	2	Will be procured from the gardening market
C	Filtration	A,B	2	Search for tips in preparing.
D	Evaporation of Ethanol Solvent using Rotary Evaporator	C	2	Search for tips on planting.
E	Preparation 0.05 M McFarland Standard for <i>S. aureus</i> Inoculum	D	20	Let it grow, researchers will check planting area weekly
F	Preparation Nutrient Broth for <i>S. aureus</i> Inoculum	-	4	Will be procured from the local wet market
G	Adjustment of Turbidity and Comparison of <i>S. aureus</i> Inoculum	F	5	Will happen in the house of one of the researchers. Should be cleaned thoroughly and dried.F
H	Preparation of Nutrient Agar	G	3	Will happen in the house of one of the researchers. Should be cleaned thoroughly and dried.
I	Cotton Swabbing of <i>S. aureus</i> on Nutrient Agar	H	1	The fertilizer will be applied using the two different methods, direct and foliar
J	Application of <i>M. calabura</i> Flower Extract using Paper Disc	H	1	The fertilizer will be applied using the method the fertilizer is instructed to use

	Diffusion Method			
K	Observance of the presence of a Zone of Inhibition (ZOI)	I,J	7	Let it grow, researchers will check planting area weekly
L	Data Collection and Analysis	K	3	Data tables and graphs

Appendix J

Table 9. Risk Management Plan

RISK FACTOR	RISK MANAGEMENT
<p>Data collection challenges Data gathering is an important step in this process since it offers the empirical framework through which research findings are constructed. The study schedule may be extended if it is difficult to collect sufficient and reliable data.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To reduce delays caused by data, put effective data collecting and management mechanisms in place.
<p>Mistakes of researchers while implementing the experiment Implementing experiments, where researchers gather evidence, is an essential part of this research process. Unfortunately, mistakes can happen to researchers too, and mistakes made during the experimental process might have serious consequences. Correction for errors made by the researchers during the experiment or data processing may take more time.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To avoid mistakes, make sure that the researchers are properly trained and set clear protocols. - Maintain consistency by implementing defined operating practices
<p>Unexpected circumstances Unexpected events or circumstances may interfere with the progress of project implementation for a class in a variety of ways. These occurrences frequently occur</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create a backup plan in case unexpected events prevent research from proceeding as planned. - Being organized and having a plan in place will assist you in navigating and

outside of the researchers' control and may be caused by social, technological, and personal variables.	overcoming unexpected events to your objectives.
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Appendix K

Figure 6. Report of Microbiological Analysis of *Muntingia calabura* flower extract on *Staphylococcus aureus* using paper disc diffusion method

REPORT OF MICROBIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

Request Reference No. : R13-032025-MIC-0139
Location of Testing : In-house
Date Submitted : March 12, 2025
Date of Analysis : March 13, 2025- March 14, 2025
Date of Issue : March 14, 2025
Sample Submitted : *Muntingia calabura* Flower ethanolic extract
Submitted by : Francheska Y. Collantes
Address : Philippine Science High School - CRC
Tiniguisan-Ampeyan, Butuan City, Agusan del Norte
Contact Number : N/A
Page : Page 1 of 2

Sample Code	Sample	Description	Parameter	Result Zone of Inhibition (mm)
MIC-0263	<i>Muntingia calabura</i> Flower ethanolic extract	15mL unchilled extract stored in glass container	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	
			Trial 1	29
			Trial 2	31
			Trial 3	28
			Average	29
			Analysis of Result:	
			<10mm, inactive	
			10-13mm, partially active	
			14-19mm, active	
			>19mm, very active	

Volume of extract : 15 mL
Culture collection number : *Staphylococcus aureus* (BIOTECH 1582)

METHODOLOGY:

The procedure for the conduct of Antimicrobial Screening was obtained from the book entitled "A Guidebook to Plant Screening: Phytochemical and Biological". The Assay method used was paper disc diffusion using 6mm diameter disc.

DP-026-F2
Revision 11/14/25/2024

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REMARKS:

The results given in this report are those obtained at the time of test and refer only to the particular sample submitted. This report shall not be reproduced, except in full, without the written approval of the laboratory.

All texts in *italics* are information obtained from the customer.

ANALYZED BY:

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Laboratory Analyst

**CERTIFIED CORRECT AND
ISSUED UNDER THE AUTHORITY OF:**

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CURRICULUM VITAE

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Elementary: With High Honors

High School: Director's List

School Clubs and Organizations Involved in High School:

PSHS - CRC Peer Facilitators Club (Member) A.Y 2019 - 2020

PSHS - CRC Indoor Sports Club (Secretary) A.Y 2022 - 2023

PSHS-CRC The Thirteenth Scholars (Member) A. Y 2023-2024

PSHS-CRC Caraga Iskolar (Editorial Section Chief) A. Y 2024-2025